

Perceptual and acoustic identification of units in unintelligible speech - Fast or slow, accurate or sloppy?

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Abstract

In the study of disordered speech, standard quantifications of speech production are not applicable to unintelligible speech. Acknowledging the value of quantifying speech production also in unintelligible speech portions, we investigate if units (syllables/consonants) can be reliably identified (perceptually and acoustically) in unintelligible speech. Our results show that listeners are both more accurate and faster in counting syllables than in counting consonants in unintelligible speech, thus indicating the syllable as a more appropriate basic unit in quantitative descriptions of unintelligible speech. Regarding acoustic analysis, we identify two existing tools as candidates for reliable identification of syllables in unintelligible speech.

Introduction

Investigations of disordered speech typically rely on measures describing the phonetic or phonemic quality of speech, often expressed in terms of speech accuracy. The standard measure for speech accuracy is the Percentage of Consonants Correct (PCC; Shriberg & Kwiatkowski, 1982), which is often used as a gold standard for describing speech before and after treatment (e.g. Allen, 2013), or to categorize different levels of impairment (e.g. Shriberg et al., 2010). Hence, a quantitative measure of *speech production* is central in the study of speech disorders.

Given that intelligible speech is often a long-term goal in speech and language intervention (Lousada, Jesus, Hall & Joffe, 2014), *intelligibility* is also a

central measure in the context of disordered speech. The gold standard measure of intelligibility has been suggested by Gordon-Brannan and Hodson (2000) as the percentage of words understood in continuous speech.

Figure 1. Two hypothetical speech samples with a PCC of 60%, but where one (A) is considerably less intelligible than the other (B).

In order for speech assessments to be representative of speech in daily life, spontaneous speech production is often the preferred speech material (Tomasello & Stahl, 2004). A challenge when using relational measures of speech production (like the PCC) is that its calculation requires knowledge of intended target words, in order to determine the degree to which these targets were met. However, when intelligibility is reduced in spontaneous speech, target words are not accessible. Therefore, unintelligible portions of speech are excluded from the analysis. Figure 1 illustrates two scenarios characterized by the same PCC, but with different levels of intelligibility. As illustrated, relational measures of speech production leave parts of the speech signal unaccounted for, and analyses of the relationship between speech production and intelligibility consequently obscured.

By necessity, measures of speech production characterizing unintelligible speech portions must be independent of assumed targets. Instead, such measures need to rely on identifiable units, such as segments or syllables. One possibility, inspired by the PCC, is to appoint consonants as the basic unit. Hence, one could estimate the *proportion of intelligible and correct consonants* from the total number of consonants in a sample, where the remainder would represent consonants that did not hit identifiable targets. Alternatively, syllables could be appointed the unit of interest, allowing the possibility to estimate the *proportion of intelligible and correct syllables* from the total number of syllables in a sample. Regardless of what unit is preferred, the identification of the underlying units needs to be both practicable and accurate.

Clearly, automatic identification of syllables and/or segments, based on acoustic analysis, would be ideal in terms of practicability. Unfortunately, however, this is still an unresolved challenge, making accuracy questionable. Although technology develops continuously, we are not aware of any recent evaluations of automatic identification of syllables and/or segments.

Aim

We seek to identify the most appropriate unit for descriptions of unintelligible speech, both in terms of practicability and accuracy. Further, we aim to provide an updated review of existing tools for automatic identification of syllables. The following research questions are investigated:

1. Given sequences of unintelligible speech, are listeners (a) more accurate and (b) faster, in counting syllables than in counting consonants?
 - 1.a. Do evaluation speed and accuracy vary across speech data: babbling, unintelligible speech, and intelligible speech?

2. Given currently available acoustic tools for automatic identification of syllables and/or consonants, how accurate are they?

Method

Speech material

Three datasets were included: BAB(BLING), INT(ELLIGIBLE) speech and UNINT(ELLIGIBLE) speech. The BAB samples were obtained from 6 infants (all 10 months old), collected from a larger project's recordings of infant-caretaker interactions. Following descriptions in e.g. Davis & MacNeilage (1995) and Fasolo, Majorano & D'Orico (2008), utterances were extracted that a) contained at least one CV syllable with a "speech-like" shape, b) were bounded by 1 sec of silence, breath or adult speech.

INT and UNINT samples were obtained from conversations between children and an SLP. INT samples were collected from three children (aged 5;6 to 7;0) with typical speech and language development, and UNINT samples were obtained from 16 children (aged 4;4 to 8;9; mean age: 6;1) with speech sound disorders. For these recordings, master transcripts had been constructed by the SLP conducting the recordings, in collaboration with the children's caregivers, in order to decipher as much of the speech as possible. Speech portions that remained unintelligible, even after parental consulting, were eligible for inclusion in the UNINT dataset.

A total of 215 BAB utterances, 70 INT utterances, and 87 UNINT utterances were extracted. From each of the three datasets, 20 utterances were selected to form a total of 60 samples – 20 triplets matching as far as possible with regards to duration. The total duration (min-max) was 48.5 s (1.6-5.05 s) for the BAB dataset, 49.0 s (1.63-5.16 s) for the INT dataset and 48.0 s (1.6-5.05) for the UNINT dataset.

Ground truth reference

The 60 speech samples were analyzed perceptually by the first author, a native

Italian speaker with phonetic training, but without knowledge of Swedish. Hence, to this individual, all datasets were unintelligible. The analysis was conducted in Praat, with visual support from the spectrogram representation of the spoken signal. Through this analysis, consonants and syllables were identified and labeled. These annotations were used as a ground truth reference to which subsequent analyses – perceptual and acoustic – were compared. A 25% subset (5 randomly selected utterances from each dataset) of the speech material was also perceptually analyzed by a Brazilian Portuguese speaker, also with phonetic training but without knowledge of Swedish. The agreement between the two annotators on the number of syllables in this subset was $r_s(15) = .94$, $p < .001$, and for consonants $r_s(15) = .88$, $p < .001$. The first author re-analyzed the same 25% subset after one month, allowing calculation of intra-annotator agreement. The agreement between first and second counting of syllables was $r_s(15) = .98$, $p < .001$, and for consonants $r_s(15) = .95$, $p < .001$.

Average speech rates were calculated, based on the ground truth reference, showing that speech rate varied across datasets, from 1.87 sylls/s in the BAB dataset, to 2.88 sylls/s in UNINT, to 3.49 sylls/s in INT.

Perceptual evaluation

Three listeners recruited from the SLP education program provided their syllable and consonant counts for all samples. Because of difficulties in recruitment, responses collected from two pilot listeners (authors AMA and SS) were also included. (The pilot listeners followed the same procedure as the other listeners, with the exception that no duplicates were included in their datasets.) All five listeners had Swedish as their strongest language; four of the five listeners had no hearing impairment, whereas one stated a non-diagnosed mild hearing loss that did not compromise her ability to perform in the task.

The listeners were fitted with headphones, and instructed to listen to the samples, and for each sample, to note the number of counted units (syllables or consonants) in an Excel sheet. For each dataset, the listeners provided first their syllable counts, and then their consonant counts, or vice versa. (Task order was balanced across listeners.)

The listeners controlled the playback themselves, and could pause the playback at any time, but were not allowed to go back to replay parts of samples. They could listen to each sample twice, maximally.

The test leader registered the time when each listener started and finished a task/listening script. (Unfortunately, the timing information from the pilot trials was not reliably registered, and consequently excluded from analysis.)

Intra-listener agreement between listeners' first and repeated syllable counts was $r_s(36) = .83$; $p < .001$. For consonant counts, intra-listener agreement was $r_s(36) = .79$; $p < .001$.

Acoustic evaluation

Candidates for acoustic evaluation were sought online and through a collegial survey. Three available tools were identified, and included in the evaluation: *Prosogram* (PROS, Mertens, 2004), *Count Infant Syllables* (CIS, Warlaimont & Ramsdell-Hudock, 2016) and *Praat Vocal Toolkit* (PVT; Corretge, 2019). For identification of syllables, all acoustic analyses were run on all three datasets. For identification of consonants, only candidates requiring known target words were available. As the aim of the study was to analyze unintelligible speech, i.e. without knowledge of target words, acoustic analysis with regards to consonants was not conducted.

PROS was run by default settings to obtain an acoustic segmentation into syllable-sized elements, except for an adjustment of f_0 detection range changed from the default 0-450 Hz to 150-800 Hz, in order to better match the infant and child speakers' f_0 levels. The same was done for CIS, in which pitch range

was changed from the default 30-450 Hz to 150-800 Hz. For PVT, the script for “mark regions by syllables” was run, by default settings, as we found no convenient way of making user adjustments.

In order for the acoustic analysis to run, all 20 utterances within each dataset were concatenated into a single wav file. Before the acoustic analysis, these three audio files were adjusted through Sopran (Tolvan Data 2019) by setting FSD to -30 to make the maximum amplitude equivalent for all samples.

Analysis

As the distribution of listener responses was not normal, non-parametric tests were used for analyses involving these variables. Accuracy of counts was estimated by Spearman’s correlation analyses, with stronger correlation to the ground truth interpreted as reflecting higher accuracy.

In order to analyze the potential difference in time required for the two counting tasks, a two-way ANOVA was conducted, with time as the dependent variable, and task (syllable count vs. consonant count) and dataset (BAB vs. UNINT vs. INT) as independent variables.

Intra-listener agreement was examined via a Spearman’s correlation analysis, based on listeners’ responses on 12 duplicated samples.

Results

Perceptual evaluation

Contrary to expectation, there was not a clear pattern of syllable counts being more accurate than consonant counts (Table 1). Notably, averaged across datasets, no listener’s syllable counts fall below a .70 agreement with the ground truth, signifying a high correlation (Mukaka, 2012). For one listener (B), consonant counts only reach a moderate agreement of .54. Yet, these single observations cannot clearly differentiate between the two tasks.

When examining datasets separately, counts are more accurate in BAB samples, compared to INT and UNINT samples. Further, consonant counts in UNINT samples showed the weakest correlation to the ground truth reference.

Regarding the time for completing the tasks, there was a significant difference between counting syllables and counting consonants: $F(1,12) = 10.79$; $p < .01$, such that syllable counts were completed faster than consonant counts ($M = 600$ s vs. 730 s). Further, as illustrated in Figure 2, there was a significant difference between datasets: $F(2,12) = 18.58$; $p < .001$, such that counting units in BAB samples required significantly less time ($M = 506$ s) than in INT ($M = 797$ s) and UNINT ($M = 693$ s) samples.

Table 1. Spearman’s correlation coefficients between each listener (A-E) vs. ground truth, for syllable counts and consonant counts, respectively, overall, and across each of the three datasets BAB(BLING), UNINT(ELLIGIBLE), and INT(ELLIGIBLE). (Each dataset including 20 samples)

Task	Listener					Avg
	A	B	C	D	E	
Syll.Count	.77**	.93**	.87**	.93**	.90**	.95**
BAB	.87**	.83**	.88**	.88**	.84**	.86**
UNINT	.66**	.83**	.84**	.93**	.74**	.90**
INT	.35	.90**	.77**	.77**	.89**	.91**
Cons.Count	.83**	.54**	.94**	.89**	.71**	.91**
BAB	.80**	.78**	.94**	.88**	.89**	.94**
UNINT	.41	.07	.83**	.66**	.45	.70**
INT	.69**	.42	.85**	.88**	.80**	.90**

** $p < .001$

Figure 2. Average duration of listener tasks (in seconds) for the three datasets (BAB, INT and UNINT), across the two tasks consonant count vs. syllable count.

Acoustic evaluation

As Table 2 shows, none of the three acoustical tools provide syllable counts as strongly correlated to the ground truth as those provided by human listeners. Mirroring the perceptual analysis, however, there is a difference between datasets; whereas acoustic syllable counts in UNINT samples reach high agreement (Mukaka, 2012) when estimated by PROS and CIS, acoustic syllable counts in BAB and INT samples do not, regardless of what tool is used.

Table 2. Correlations for each of the three acoustical tools (PROS, CIS and PVT) vs. ground truth, for syllable counts overall, and for the BAB(BLING), UNINT(ELLIGIBLE) and INT(ELLIGIBLE) datasets separately. Correlations for perceptual syllable counts vs. ground truth are given for reference.

	PROS	CIS	PVT	Perc
Overall	.59**	.61**	.60**	.95**
BAB	-.02	.03	.60**	.86**
UNINT	.85**	.84**	.66**	.90**
INT	.47*	.41	.68**	.91**

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Discussion

Our aim was to identify the most appropriate unit for quantifying unintelligible speech – both in terms of feasibility and of accuracy – and to compare unintelligible speech to other types of speech data. As expected, listeners were faster

in counting syllables than counting consonants – regardless of dataset. Further, listeners were faster in evaluating BAB samples compared to the other datasets. It is possible that the lower speech rate in the BAB dataset could explain the faster task execution. Regarding accuracy, results differed between datasets. When only considering UNINT speech samples, listeners were found to be more accurate when counting syllables than when counting consonants. However, for INT samples and BAB samples, listeners’ consonant counts were almost as accurate as their syllable counts. We see no obvious explanation to this pattern. It should be underlined that our findings are based on a small number of listeners; more listeners should be included to ensure more stable results.

Regarding the acoustic analyses, results show that for the UNINT dataset, PROS and CIS reached high accuracy, and are therefore both relevant as candidates for automatic identification of syllables. For BAB and INT, on the other hand, none of the included tools reached sufficient accuracy. In this context, it should be noted that the acoustic conditions were not comparable across datasets; the BAB recordings were of lower quality than in the INT and UNINT datasets. However, we see no apparent reason why accuracy is so low in the INT dataset.

Conclusions

Although based on a small group of listeners, our results indicate that when choosing between syllables and consonants as the basic unit in quantifying unintelligible speech, syllables are recommended, as listeners are both more accurate and faster. As for acoustic identification of syllables in unintelligible speech, tools exist that provide reliable estimates.

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